

ИГРА КАК НАИБОЛЕЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЙ МЕТОД В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

GAME AS THE MOST EFFECTIVE METHOD IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

ГЕРАЙЗАДЕ МАЛАХАТ АГА БАБА КЫЗЫ,

к.ф.н., доцент,

Азербайджанский медицинский университет.

КАДИЕВА СЕВДА АБДУЛСАМЕД КЫЗЫ,

к.ф.н., старший преподаватель,

Азербайджанский медицинский университет.

ДАШДАМИРОВА НИГЯР МАГАМЕД КЫЗЫ,

к.ф.н., преподаватель,

Азербайджанский медицинский университет.

GERAYZADE MALAHAT AGHA BABA KYZY,

Ph.D., Associate Professor,

Azerbaijan Medical University.

KADIEVA SEVDA ABDULSAMED KYZY,

Ph.D., Senior lecturer,

Azerbaijan Medical University.

DASHDAMIROVA NIGAR MAGAMED KYZY,

Ph.D., teacher,

Azerbaijan Medical University.

Статья посвящена игре, как наиболее эффективному методу обучения иностранному языку. Авторы показывают, что игра является формой обучения, которая не только повышает качество учебного процесса, но и раскрывает личность человека, его творческий потенциал. Исходя из анализа методики обучения иностранному языку за рубежом, выявлено, что в основе обучения иностранному языку лежит игровой метод. Основной функцией игровых и дебатных методов обучения является тренировка ума, внимания, восприятия информации, гуманного отношения к партнеру. Это, в свою очередь, развивает языковые навыки.

The article is devoted to the most effective method in foreign language teaching – game. The authors show that game is the form of teaching which not only improves the quality of teaching process, but also discovers identity of a person, his creative potential. Based on the analysis of the method of foreign language teaching abroad, it was revealed that the basis of teaching a foreign language is a game method. The main function of game and debate methods of teaching is training of mind, attention, information perception, humanity relationship with the partner. It also develops language skills.

Ключевые слова: учебный процесс, общение, игра, речевые навыки, беседа, речевые обороты, диалог, дискуссия, результативность, основная цель.

Key words: *teaching process, communication, game, speech skills, conversation, speech patterns, dialogue, debate, effectiveness, the main goal.*

At present much attention is turned to searching new forms, ways and methods of foreign language teaching. We need such forms of teaching which could not only improve the quality of the teaching process, but also discover identity of a person, his creative potential.

In foreign language teaching a special attention should be paid on the development of active speech communication with use of modern technical aids of training.

Communicative method destroys the psychological barrier between the teacher and the student. And when the students stop feel a distance between the teacher and themselves, when they are interested, when it is pleasant to communicate with the teacher – it becomes easier to begin to speak foreign language.

Many scientists as Puchkova U.Y., Konesheva A.V., Dianova Y.M. and others consider, game the most effective way in foreign language teaching.

Game can outgrow in creation, in the model of human relations. The use of game method raises effectiveness of foreign language teaching. It can be used for revision of the old material and it is better to carry out at the end of the lesson in order to get down the straining. It is important that the games at the lesson make positive emotions. During the game students shouldn't be interrupted, as it destroys the atmosphere of communication. Being interrupted for mistake the student not only loses the main idea of his utterance, but also a wish to continue the conversation. The corrections should be done at the end of the lesson.

Altogether the use of different games at foreign language lessons contributes to mastering the language in entertaining form, develops memory, attention, gumption and interest to the language. At the same time the games must be used at the foreign language lessons for activation of speech activity.

The game method brings animation into the teaching process, supports positive emotions of the students, increases their motivation.

This is a great motivation for learning foreign language. The topics of the game may be:

The Place Where You Live

Everyday Problems

At the Chemist's

At the Doctor's

Your Favorite Holiday

Our Future Profession

Health and Fitness

Asking the Way

Before the game comes thematic preparation of the students and vocabulary revision of conversational forms and phrasal verbs.

Playing different games the dialogue form the student are given special expressions for requests, permission, suggestions, agreeing or disagreeing, likes, dislikes, preferences, greetings, farewells and others (Table 1).

For apologies, excuses and thanks the students are give the following patterns and they use them in the dialogues during games:

Apologies with common replies

We can apologies [say sorry] in different ways in different situations.

A: I'm(terribly/really)sorry– *Terribly/really makes you sound 'more sorry'*

I've forgotten your book.

B: Never mind. That's OK.

A: I beg your pardon –I didn’t see you there. *I beg your pardon is a more formal apology, often used if you walk into someone.*

B: That’s all right. (also That’s OK.)

A: (I’m)sorry to disturb you. *We use this phrase when we interrupt/ speak to someone who is busy working.*

B: Don’t worry. Come on in. I can finish this later.

A: (I’m)sorry to keep you waiting – I won’t be long. *We use this phrase when someone is waiting for us. I won’t be long = I will be with you very soon.*

B: OK. Fine.

A: Excuse me, I won’t be a minute. *We use this phrase when we have to leave a room or go somewhere.*

B: OK. Fine.

A: I must apologise for the noise last night. *This is a more formal apology, and it is often used in business letters.*

B: That’s all right. I understand.

A: I’m (really) sorry I’m late.

B: Don’t worry. *Common mistakes I’m sorry I’m late. (NOT I’m sorry for belate. OR I’m sorryto belate)*

Table 1. Likes and dislikes

	agree	Disagree
I love rock music. I’m really into dance music. [like it very much; infml] I like a lot of pop music.	So do I. / Me too. So am I. / Me too. So do I. / Me too.	Really? I don’t. Really? I’m not. Do you? I hate it.
I quite like salsa and samba. I don’t mind jazz. [it’s OK]	So do I. / Me too. Yeah, it’s OK.	Oh, I’m not very keen. Oh, I can’t stand it.
I’m not very keen on folk music. I can’t stand classical music. [dislike it very much; infml] I hate opera.	Neither am I. / Me neither. Neither can I. / Me neither. So do I. / Me too.	Really? I love it. Really? I quite like it.

The performed dialogues better invented by the students themselves. Here language mastering level, creative, approach and professional skills are evaluated. Planing foreign language lessons it is necessary not only to try to enlarge the students’ vocabulary, but also to formulate all circumstances for individual development of each person.

In order to make the lesson more interesting and more effective the use of innovative methods or modern technology is also necessary. It will let the teacher interest the students in foreign language learning and succeed their ability to communicate fluently in it.

Role games increase the interest to the subject taking possession of speech skills in natural communicative situations. It develops the students’ communicatory abilities and foreign language mastering. The ultimatum in this process is free orientation in alien environment and competence of adequate response in various situations.

Investigating the method of foreign language teaching abroad it was detected that the bases of foreign language teaching is game method.

The modern teacher must not only have a deep knowledge in language teaching, but also be an actress and at the same time a director whose main goal at this process is creation of conditions of practical mastering of any language for each student, choosing the method letting the student show his potency and creativity, the use of Internet resources. With its further analyses by game method.

The plan of the lesson must be formed heeding professional orientation of the students.

It must be based on standart syllabus added with thematical dialogues, situations and exercises. This is a great motivation for language lerning. The lesson may be organized in group form like situational dialogues, krasfords, role games using plenty of various conversational models.

Participating in a debate is also useful in foreign language teaching.

The group is devided into two teams which should debate the motion, while the rest of the group acts as the audience and judges, whose task is summarizing the outcome of the discussion. The topics may be the followings:

“ Medical Service in Azerbaijan and in Your Native Country”

“Advantages and Disadvantages of City and Country Life”

“Tell about a Recent Event That Made You Happy”

“Talk about Your Leisure Activity”

“Do You Like Music? What Type of Music do You Listen Often?”

“What is the Most Interesting Part of Your Home Area?”

The main function of game and debate methods of teaching is training of mind, attention, information perception, humanity relationship with the partner. It also develops language skills. The principal function of it is psychological which removes any barriers in this process. All functions are derected to the harmonic development of a person and first of all help in teaching foreign language. Game method is maximally close to real life. It is the highest type of pedagogical activity. The most difficult component of teacher’s work in organization of role game is creating the speaking motive.

During game the students start to understand complex relationships. They start to understand they are only one part of a bigger picture.

The student gains understanding of the rules of the game to be successful in the activity. He also starts to understand the expectations of them in a given situation. In other words, he starts to think about what other people may be thinking.

According to George Herbert Meads theory “games develop self by allowing individuals to understand & adhere to the rules of the activity. Self is developed by understanding that there are rules in which one must abide by in order to win the game or be successful at an activity” [1].

Taking on different roles, a person is able to internalize the perspective of others and develop an understanding of how others feel about themselves and others in a variety of social situations.

This is a very important stage for the development of the self because it makes the individual take on the roles of everyone. By doing this, it teaches the individual to function in an organized group and to determine what their role, or contribution to the group, will be as they are given this time to figure out what the role suits them best. As well, organization and personality emerge while at the stage.

As the students’ selves develop more and more, the begin to be able to examine their own thoughts.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. G.H. Mead. Mind. Self and Society. United States. University of Chicago Press., 1934. 439 p.
2. Xarici dilin tədrisi metodikasının bəzi istiqamətləri. “Azərbaycan məktəbi”, №5. 2014.

3. Будатова Д.В. Иностранный язык как средство профессиональной подготовки студентов неязыковых вузов // Профессиональное образование, 1996. №1. С.78-83.

© Герайзаде М. А. Б. К., Кадиева С.А.К., Даидамирова Н. М. К., 2023.